

IMPLEMENTATION OF SCHOOL-BASED MANAGEMENT OF SELECTED PUBLIC ELEMENTARY SCHOOLS IN DISTRICT II-D ANTİPOLO CITY

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Implementation of School-Based Management of Selected Public Elementary Schools in District II-D Antipolo City

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Abstract

This study aimed to determine the implementation of school-based management of selected public elementary schools in District II-D Antipolo City, which served as input for an action plan for the school year 2025-2026. Regarding leadership and governance, the teacher-respondents got a composite mean of 3.67, while the parent-respondents got 3.59, both verbally interpreted as very strongly Agreeing. In terms of curriculum and learning, the teacher-respondents got a composite mean of 3.67, while the parent-respondents got 3.76, both of which were verbally interpreted as very strongly Agreeing. In terms of accountability and continuous improvement, the teacher-respondents got a composite mean of 3.44, while the parent-respondents got 3.68, both of which were verbally interpreted as very strongly Agreeable. In terms of resource management, the teacher-respondents got a composite mean of 3.7, while the parent-respondents got 3.70, both of which were verbally interpreted as very strongly agreeing. Significant Differences: the study identified notable disparities in the perceptions of the two groups of respondents regarding the implementation of school-based management, particularly in the areas of leadership and governance, curriculum and learning, accountability and continuous improvement, and management of resources. The two groups of respondents' perceptions are similar regarding the implementation of school-based management concerning the above-cited variables, except for the Management of Resources.

Keywords: *curriculum, governance, leadership*

Introduction

In the Philippines, the Department of Education is pursuing policy reforms under the Basic Education Sector Reform Agenda (BESRA) to achieve the Education for All (EFA) objectives by 2019. Key Reform Thrust 1 (KRT1) of BESRA, School-Based Management (SBM), is a collaborative effort. It underscores the empowerment of key stakeholders in school communities, making them integral to the process of continuous improvement of schools. Their active participation is crucial in the journey towards the attainment of higher pupil/student learning outcomes (Abulencia, n.d.; Department of Education, 2019).

Within SBM, several enabling policies were formulated, such as the School Governing Council (SGC), conduct of Assessment of Level of Practice, School Improvement Planning (SIP), and reporting of accomplishments through School Reports Cards (SRCs). These policies were supported by a budget line item in the General Appropriations Act (GAA) for the installation of SBM in all public elementary and secondary schools.

With this, SBM has been revised to better highlight the learner as the center of SBM practice to encompass the diverse realities of learning contexts defined and uniquely occurring within specific geographic, social, cultural, economic, political, and environmental make-up of the contemporary society; and to enhance the commitment of education stakeholders at all levels to their responsibilities and accountabilities in realizing the education outcomes for children. This commitment is system-sent to the dedication of the education community to the cause of improving school performance and achieving the Education for All/Millennium Development Goals (Department of Education, 2020).

School-Based Management is a DepEd thrust that decentralizes the decision-making from the Central Office and field offices to individual schools to enable them to better respond to their specific education needs. It formally recognizes the expertise and competence of those who work in individual schools to make decisions to improve learning. It also gives teachers, other staff members, and the community increased input into decisions. Thus, schoolteacher management positively affects teachers' students' teaching profession and academic achievements.

It is on these essential points that the researcher was urged to conduct administrators public elementary school administrators' school-based management practices about school performance to determine the extent of implementation of the different school-based management practices; to determine if the school-based management practices applied by the school administrators are contributory factors that can effectively help improve the school performance.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the implementation of School-Based Management of selected public elementary schools in District II-D Antipolo City which served as inputs for an action plan during the school year 2025-2026. More specifically, it sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the perception of the teachers and parents as regards the implementation of school-based management in terms of the

following:

- 1.1. leadership and governance;
- 1.2. curriculum and learning;
- 1.3. accountability and continuous improvement; and
- 1.4. management of resources?
2. Is there a significant difference between the perceptions of the two groups of respondents as regards the implementation of school-based management with respect to the above-cited variables?
3. Based on the results of the study, what action plan may be proposed?

Methodology

Research Design

This study, using a descriptive survey research design, aims to answer the question: What are the school-based management practices of public elementary school administrators, and how do they relate to school performance?

According to Williams (2019), Descriptive research aims to describe a population, situation, or phenomenon accurately and systematically. It can answer what, where, when, and how questions, but not why questions. It involves the description, recording, analysis, and interpretation of phenomena' present nature, composition, or processes. The focus is on prevailing conditions or how a person, group, or thing currently behaves or functions.

Therefore, through the use of descriptive research design, the research can describe the effectiveness of the public elementary school administrators' school-based management practices about school performance.

Respondents

This study, using a descriptive survey research design, aims to answer the question: What are the school-based management practices of public elementary school administrators, and how do they relate to school performance?

According to Williams (2019), Descriptive research aims to describe a population, situation, or phenomenon accurately and systematically. It can answer what, where, when, and how questions, but not why questions. It involves the description, recording, analysis, and interpretation of phenomena' present nature, composition, or processes. The focus is on prevailing conditions or how a person, group, or thing currently behaves or functions.

Therefore, through the use of descriptive research design, the research can describe the effectiveness of the public elementary school administrators' school-based management practices about school performance.

Instrument

The study used a researcher-made questionnaire and descriptive questions that served as indicators in every variable. The survey questionnaire consisted of three parts. The first part contained the evaluation of the respondents. The second part contained the comments and suggestions of the parents and teacher-respondents.

The questionnaires that served as survey instruments of the study were validated by experts to ensure their correctness and validity. The questionnaire's contents were analyzed and scrutinized by principals, master teachers, English teachers, and education program supervisors. Their comments and feedback were considered in the final approval of the method and were examined by the consultant again as the researcher's proofreader.

Procedure

Permission from the concerned authorities was sought before the study was conducted. Upon approval of the school's division superintendent and the principal, the questionnaire – checklists were administered to the parents and teacher-respondents from the selected public high schools in Antipolo City and were personally retrieved by the researcher.

Data Analysis

Frequency, Percentage Distribution, and Ranking. This were used to analyze and summarize the results of the responses from the questionnaire.

t-Test. This was used to determine the significant difference between the perceptions of the two groups of respondents as regards the implementation of school-based management with respect to Leadership and Governance, Curriculum and Learning, Accountability and Continuous Improvement, and Management of Resources.

Results and Discussion

This section provided the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of the gathered data from the questionnaires answered by the respondents in accordance with the specific questions posited on the objectives of the study.

Perception of the teachers as regards the implementation of school-based management

Perception of the teachers as regards the implementation of school-based management in terms of Leadership and Governance.

Table 1. *Perception of the teachers as regards the implementation of school-based management in terms of Leadership and Governance*

<i>The school...</i>	<i>A. Leadership and Governance</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Rank</i>
1. considers a mechanism that allows the development of a shared vision, mission, and goals (VMG) which reflects the aspirations and thrusts of the community.		3.748	Very Strongly Agree	2
2. revisits periodically the organization's vision, direction, and aspirations and adjust by the learning managers, learning facilitators and community stakeholders to respond to the community's conditions and emerging needs.		3.735	Very Strongly Agree	3
3. encourages stakeholders to actively participate through dialogue and/or consensus-building in formulating relevant policies and guidelines in conducting regular view and updating of community initiatives.		3.77	Very Strongly Agree	1
4. knows that the organizational structure for education governance promotes ownership of goals and members assumed particular roles and responsibilities to carry out initiatives.		3.6	Very Strongly Agree	4
5. encourages the community to facilitate the development of an education plan based on its vision, direction, and aspirations.		3.505	Very Strongly Agree	5
	Composite Mean	3.67	Very Strongly Agree	

As discussed in Table 1, the respondents stated that the school encourages stakeholders to actively participate through dialogue and/or consensus-building, in formulating relevant policies and guidelines in conducting regular view and updating of community initiatives, which got the highest weighted mean of 3.77 and the highest rank of 1. The findings suggested that the school encourages stakeholders to actively participate through dialogue and consensus-building in formulating relevant policies and guidelines and conducting regular reviews and updates of community initiatives. This inclusive approach reflects the school's commitment to fostering collaboration and engagement among all members of the school community, including parents, teachers, students, and other stakeholders. By involving stakeholders in the policy-making process, the school ensures that diverse perspectives are considered, leading to more comprehensive and effective policies and guidelines. Dialogue and consensus-building facilitate open communication, mutual understanding, and shared responsibility for the school's initiatives and goals. Phil (2023) stated that school Leadership Teams should delegate greater responsibility and balance principle, purpose, and people, with distributed leadership and local governance support.

However, the said group of respondents stated that the school encourages the community to facilitate the development of an education plan based on its vision, direction, and aspirations which yielded the least weighted mean of 3.505 and least rank of 5. The findings suggested that the school encourages the community to facilitate the development of an education plan based on its vision, direction, and aspirations. This inclusive approach reflects the school's commitment to aligning its educational strategies with the collective goals and values of the community it serves. By involving the community in the development of the education plan, the school ensures that the plan is comprehensive and reflective of the community's unique needs and aspirations. This collaborative effort helps in creating a shared vision and a unified direction for the school's educational objectives. According to Alvarez et al. (2023), school heads' instructional leadership and parent and community involvement significantly influence school management and governance, with students and teachers agreeing on the importance of these factors.

The composite mean of 3.67 implied that the perception of the teachers as regards the implementation of school-based management in terms of Leadership and Governance is within high level. The findings suggested that the perception of teachers regarding school-based management practices in terms of leadership and governance is at a high level. This indicates that teachers view the school's leadership and governance practices positively, recognizing their effectiveness in guiding and managing the school. Effective school governance involves ensuring the legitimacy of schools as institutions through institutionalization processes, with six specific principles relating to work on the institutional primary task, compliance with rules, norms, and accountability for school functioning (Connolly & James, 2022).

Perception of the teachers as regards the implementation of school-based management in terms of Curriculum and Learning

As presented in Table 2, the respondents perceived that the school urges the community to actively participate in developing and mentoring the learners' awareness and practice of good citizenship and shares in the attainment of individual and collective competencies which got the highest weighted mean of 3.877 and the highest rank of 1. The findings suggested that the school urges the community to actively participate in developing and mentoring learners' awareness and practice of good citizenship, as well as sharing in the attainment of individual and collective competencies. This approach highlights the school's commitment to fostering a strong sense of civic responsibility and community involvement among students. By encouraging community participation in citizenship education, the school ensures that students are exposed to diverse perspectives and real-life examples of good citizenship. This collaborative effort helps students understand the importance of civic engagement, ethical behavior, and social responsibility. The curriculum is a complex, multi-layered concept that operates at the policy, programmatic, and classroom levels, defining schooling's purposes and expectations (Hudson & Shelton, 2020).

Table 2. Perception of the teachers as regards the implementation of school-based management in terms of Curriculum and Learning

<i>The school...</i>	<i>B. Curriculum and Learning</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Rank</i>
1. makes sure that the implemented curriculum in school is rights-based, inclusive, culturally and developmentally appropriate to the needs and interest of the learners and community.		3.622	Very Strongly Agree	3
2. monitors regularly the learning systems together with the community using appropriate tools to ensure the holistic growth and development of the learners and the community.		3.601	Very Strongly Agree	4
3. reviews and improve continuous appropriate assessment tools for teaching and learning.		3.430	Very Strongly Agree	5
4. urges the community to actively participate in developing and mentoring the learners' awareness and practice of good citizenship and shares in the attainment of individual and collective competencies.		3.877	Very Strongly Agree	1
5. assures that methods and resources are learner and community-friendly, enjoyable, safe, inclusive, accessible, and aimed at developing self-directed learners.		3.821	Very Strongly Agree	2
	Composite Mean	3.67	Very Strongly Agree	

However, the said group of respondents observed that the school reviews and improve continuously appropriate assessment tools for teaching and learning which yielded the least weighted mean of 3.430 and least rank of 5. The findings suggested that the school continuously reviews and improves appropriate assessment tools for teaching and learning. This commitment to ongoing evaluation and enhancement of assessment methods indicates the school's dedication to maintaining high standards of educational quality and effectiveness. By regularly reviewing and updating assessment tools, the school ensures that they remain relevant, accurate, and aligned with current educational objectives and standards. This process helps in identifying areas where students may need additional support, as well as recognizing and reinforcing areas of strength. Deng (2022) stated that a future-oriented, knowledge-rich curriculum cultivates human powers, understanding, capabilities, and dispositions, preparing students for success in both present and future worlds.

The composite mean of 3.67 implied that the perception of the teachers as regards the implementation of school-based management in terms of Curriculum and Learning is within high level. The findings suggested that the perception of teachers regarding the implementation of school-based management in terms of curriculum and learning is at a high level. This indicates that teachers view the school's curriculum and learning management practices positively, recognizing their effectiveness in supporting educational outcomes and student learning experiences. According to Saleh & Kareem (2022), language and curriculum play a crucial role in meeting education objectives and changing individuals' behavior, with their relationship influencing their development, skills, and desire for learning.

Perception of the teachers as regards the implementation of school-based management in terms of Accountability and Continuous Improvement

Table 3. Perception of the teachers as regards the implementation of school-based management in terms of Accountability and Continuous Improvement

<i>The school...</i>	<i>C. Accountability and Continuous Improvement</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Rank</i>
1. presents properly the roles and responsibilities of accountable persons and collective bodies which are clearly defined and agreed upon by community stakeholders.		3.6	Very Strongly Agree	2
2. recognizes achievement goal based on a collaboratively developed performance accountability system and gaps are addressed through appropriate action.		3.4	Very Strongly Agree	4
3. enhances continuously the accountability system that is owned by the community to ensure that management structures and mechanisms are responsive to the merging learning needs and demands of the community.		3.5	Very Strongly Agree	3
4. makes sure that the accountability assessment criteria and tools, feedback mechanism, and information are inclusive and collaboratively developed and agreed upon.		3.05	Strongly Agree	5
5. performs regular participatory assessment of performance with the community.		3.65	Very Strongly Agree	1
	Composite Mean	3.44	Very Strongly Agree	

As shown in Table 3, the respondents perceived that the school performs regular participatory assessment of performance with the community which got the highest weighted mean of 3.65 and the highest rank of 1. The findings suggested that the school performs regular participatory assessments of performance with the community. This approach highlights the school's commitment to transparency, accountability, and continuous improvement through active engagement with community stakeholders. By conducting participatory assessments, the school involves parents, students, teachers, and other community members in evaluating its performance. This collaborative process ensures that diverse perspectives are considered, leading to a more comprehensive understanding of the school's strengths and areas for improvement. A leadership plan focusing on student-centered practices and learning progression, combined with individual accountability, reliability, and consistency, led to a significant improvement in student achievement at a low-performing middle school (Oropallo et al., 2023).

However, the said group of respondents stated that the school makes sure that the accountability assessment criteria and tools, feedback mechanism, and information are inclusive and collaboratively developed and agreed upon which yielded the least weighted mean of 3.05 and least rank of 5. The findings suggested that the school ensures accountability assessment criteria and tools, feedback mechanisms, and information are inclusive and collaboratively developed and agreed upon. This approach emphasizes the school's commitment to creating a transparent, equitable, and participatory system for evaluating performance and making improvements. By involving all stakeholders in the development of assessment criteria and tools, the school fosters a sense of ownership and collective responsibility. This collaborative process ensures that the criteria and tools are fair, comprehensive, and reflective of the community's diverse perspectives and needs. According to Koh et al. (2023), successful long-term school improvement strategies include purposeful program selection, strategic staff leadership, continuous professional education, accountable networks, data sharing, and supportive school culture.

The composite mean of 3.44 implied that the perception of the teachers as regards the implementation of school-based management in terms of Accountability and Continuous Improvement is within high level. The findings suggested that the perception of teachers regarding the implementation of school-based management in terms of accountability and continuous improvement is at a high level. This indicates that teachers view the school's efforts in maintaining accountability and promoting ongoing improvement positively, recognizing their effectiveness in fostering a high-quality educational environment. Jabeen et al. (2023) stated that educational accountability is challenging, with ambiguity in roles and responsibilities among stakeholders, and performance-based accountability is recommended for enhancing student learning and success.

Perception of the teachers as regards the implementation of school-based management in terms of Management of Resources

Table 4. *Perception of the teachers as regards the implementation of school-based management in terms of Management of Resources*

<i>The school...</i>	<i>D. Management of Resources</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Rank</i>
1. undertakes collaborative regular resource inventory together with the learning managers, learning facilitators, and community stakeholders as basis for resource allocation and mobilization.		3.7	Very Strongly Agree	4
2. conducts regular dialogue for planning and resource programming that is accessible and inclusive, to continuously engage stakeholders and support the implementation of community education plans.		3.97	Very Strongly Agree	1
3. presents a community-developed resource management that drives appropriate behaviors of the stakeholders to ensure judicious, appropriate, and effective use of resources.		3.8	Very Strongly Agree	2
4. conducts regular monitoring, evaluation, and reporting processes of resource management that are collaboratively developed and jointly implemented by the learning managers, facilitators, and community stakeholders.		3.79	Very Strongly Agree	3
5. establishes a system that manages the network and linkage, strengthens and sustains partnership for improving resource management.		3.25	Strongly Agree	5
	Composite Mean	3.7	Very Strongly Agree	

As presented in Table 4, the respondents stated that the school conducts regular dialogue for planning and resource programming that is accessible and inclusive, to continuously engage stakeholders and support the implementation of community education plans which got the highest weighted mean of 3.97 and the highest rank of 1. The findings suggested that the school conducts regular dialogue for planning and resource programming that is accessible and inclusive, aimed at continuously engaging stakeholders and supporting the implementation of community education plans. This approach demonstrates the school's commitment to fostering open communication, collaboration, and active participation among all members of the school community. By holding regular dialogues, the school ensures that planning and resource allocation processes are transparent and consider the diverse needs and perspectives of all stakeholders. This inclusive practice helps in building trust, fostering mutual understanding, and promoting shared responsibility for the school's educational initiatives. School resource management effectively improves education quality by increasing the added value of input factors and empowering schools to apply an integrated problem-solving approach to management (Muliati et al., 2022).

However, the said group of respondents stated that the school establishes a system that manages the network and linkage, strengthens and sustains partnership for improving resource management which yielded the least weighted mean of 3. 3.25 and least rank of 5. The findings suggested that the school has established a system to manage networks and partnerships, aimed at strengthening and sustaining collaborations to improve resource management. This systematic approach demonstrates the school's commitment to enhancing efficiency, leveraging resources effectively, and fostering sustainable partnerships within the community. By establishing a structured system, the school ensures that networks and partnerships are managed proactively, facilitating continuous communication and collaboration among stakeholders. This helps in maximizing the use of available resources, sharing expertise, and collectively addressing challenges related to resource management. According to Bryson et al. (2020), intensive use of human resource management practices is correlated with substantial improvements in workplace performance, both among schools and other workplaces.

The composite mean of 3.7 implied that the perception of the teachers as regards the implementation of school-based management in terms of Management of Resources is within high level. The findings suggested that the perception of teachers regarding the

implementation of school-based management in terms of the management of resources is at a high level. This indicates that teachers view the school's efforts in managing resources positively, recognizing their effectiveness in ensuring efficient allocation, utilization, and sustainability of resources. Chen et al. (2021) stated the strategic resource management behaviors, such as exploring, exploiting, and pruning, predict higher academic achievement in self-regulated learners.

Perception of the parents as regards the implementation of school-based management

Perception of the parents as regards the implementation of school-based management in terms of Leadership and Governance

Table 5. Perception of the parents as regards the implementation of school-based management in terms of Leadership and Governance

<i>The school...</i>	<i>A. Leadership and Governance</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Rank</i>
1. considers a mechanism that allows the development of a shared vision, mission, and goals (VMG) which reflects the aspirations and thrusts of the community.		3.348	Very Strongly Agree	5
2. revisits periodically the organization's vision, direction, and aspirations and adjust by the learning managers, learning facilitators and community stakeholders to respond to the community's conditions and emerging needs.		3.836	Very Strongly Agree	2
3. encourages stakeholders to actively participate through dialogue and/or consensus-building in formulating relevant policies and guidelines in conducting regular view and updating of community initiatives.		3.51	Very Strongly Agree	3
4. knows that the organizational structure for education governance promotes ownership of goals and members assumed particular roles and responsibilities to carry out initiatives.		3.84	Very Strongly Agree	1
5. encourages the community to facilitate the development of an education plan based on its vision, direction, and aspirations.		3.45	Very Strongly Agree	4
Composite Mean		3.59	Very Strongly Agree	

As discussed in Table 5, the respondents stated that the school knows that the organizational structure for education governance promotes ownership of goals and members assumed particular roles and responsibilities to carry out initiatives, which got the highest weighted mean of 3.84 and the highest rank of 1. The findings indicated that the school recognized how the organizational structure for education governance promoted ownership of goals. Members assumed specific roles and responsibilities to effectively implement initiatives. This structure facilitated a clear delineation of tasks and fostered a sense of accountability among members. It ensured that each individual understood their role in contributing to the school's overarching objectives, thereby enhancing coordination and efficiency in implementing educational initiatives. By promoting ownership, the organizational structure encouraged active engagement and commitment from all stakeholders, aligning their efforts with the school's strategic direction. This understanding of roles and responsibilities within the governance framework not only clarified expectations but also empowered members to contribute meaningfully to the school's mission and vision. Increased teacher decision-making responsibilities consistently and positively impact student achievement in math, reading, and science regardless of school governance arrangements (Luschei & Jeong 2020).

However, the said group of respondents stated that the school considers a mechanism that allows the development of a shared vision, mission, and goals (VMG) which reflects the aspirations and thrusts of the community which yielded the least weighted mean of 3.348 and least rank of 5. The findings revealed that the school considered a mechanism that allowed for the development of a shared vision, mission, and goals (VMG) reflecting the aspirations and thrusts of the community. This mechanism facilitated a collaborative process where stakeholders, including faculty, students, parents, and community members, contributed to shaping the VMG. It ensured that the school's strategic direction resonated with the values and priorities of its diverse constituents, fostering a sense of inclusivity and collective ownership. By aligning the VMG with community aspirations, the school enhanced its relevance and responsiveness to local needs, promoting a unified sense of purpose among stakeholders. This collaborative approach not only strengthened stakeholder engagement but also facilitated consensus-building around key educational priorities and initiatives. As a result, the school was better positioned to implement strategic decisions that reflected the shared values and ambitions of its community, thereby promoting coherence and commitment towards achieving its educational objectives. Fajriana (2023) stated that good school governance in vocational schools can improve performance and reduce unemployment by promoting consensus-based decision-making and involving all school members.

The composite mean of 3.59 implied that the perception of the parents as regards the implementation of school-based management in terms of Leadership and Governance is within high level. The findings indicated that the perception of parents regarding the implementation of school-based management, particularly in terms of leadership and governance, was at a high level. Parents expressed confidence in the leadership's ability to effectively manage the school, ensuring transparent decision-making and accountability. They viewed the governance framework as supportive of collaborative decision-making processes that included parental input and representation. This high level of perception reflected parents' satisfaction with how leadership roles were defined and how governance structures facilitated effective communication and engagement between school management and the parent community. Parents believed that their voices were heard and considered in shaping policies and initiatives, fostering a sense of trust and partnership with the school administration. Overall, the positive perception underscored the effectiveness of school-based management practices in promoting transparency, inclusivity, and responsiveness to parental concerns and aspirations within the educational setting.

According to Allcroft (2020), effective school leadership in groupings requires a change of mindset and a focus on shared goals and objectives, rather than individual schools.

Perception of the parents as regards the implementation of school-based management in terms of Curriculum and Learning

Table 6. Perception of the parents as regards the implementation of school-based management in terms of Curriculum and Learning

<i>The school...</i>	<i>B. Curriculum and Learning</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Rank</i>
1. makes sure that the implemented curriculum in school is rights-based, inclusive, culturally and developmentally appropriate to the needs and interest of the learners and community.		3.76	Very Strongly Agree	4
2. monitors regularly the learning systems together with the community using appropriate tools to ensure the holistic growth and development of the learners and the community.		3.3	Very Strongly Agree	5
3. reviews and improve continuously appropriate assessment tools for teaching and learning.		3.95	Very Strongly Agree	2
4. urges the community to actively participate in developing and mentoring the learners' awareness and practice of good citizenship and shares in the attainment of individual and collective competencies.		3.83	Very Strongly Agree	3
5. assures that methods and resources are learner and community-friendly, enjoyable, safe, inclusive, accessible, and aimed at developing self-directed learners.		3.97	Very Strongly Agree	1
	Composite Mean	3.76	Very Strongly Agree	

As presented in Table 6 the respondents perceived that the school assures that methods and resources are learner and community-friendly, enjoyable, safe, inclusive, accessible, and aimed at developing self-directed learners which got the highest weighted mean of 3.97 and the highest rank of 1. The findings indicated that the school ensured that methods and resources were learner and community-friendly, enjoyable, safe, inclusive, accessible, and aimed at developing self-directed learners. This assurance underscored the commitment to creating an educational environment that catered to diverse learning needs and fostered a sense of belonging among all stakeholders. Methods employed were designed to engage learners actively, making learning enjoyable and relevant to their lives. Resources were accessible and inclusive, accommodating various learning styles and abilities, thereby promoting equity and equal opportunity for all students. The school prioritized safety, ensuring that learning environments were secure and conducive to effective learning experiences. The hidden curriculum in schooling, which involves informally conducted lessons, shapes individuals and society in general, impacting social and moral education (Abuzandah, 2021).

However, the said group of respondents observed that the school monitors regularly the learning systems together with the community using appropriate tools to ensure the holistic growth and development of the learners and the community which yielded the least weighted mean of 3.3 and least rank of 5. The findings indicated that the school regularly monitored learning systems together with the community, utilizing appropriate tools to ensure the holistic growth and development of both learners and the community. This monitoring process was characterized by systematic assessment and evaluation of educational initiatives, ensuring that they effectively met the evolving needs of students and community stakeholders. By involving the community in this process, the school promoted transparency and collaboration in educational planning and decision-making. The use of appropriate tools for monitoring allowed for comprehensive assessment of various aspects of learning and community development, including academic progress, social-emotional well-being, and community engagement. This holistic approach ensured that educational interventions were aligned with the broader goals of fostering well-rounded individuals who contribute positively to society. Hapsari et al. (2023) stated that curriculum changes positively impact learning outcomes and education quality but may also cause negative impacts like decreased achievement due to difficulty following new learning procedures.

The composite mean of 3.76 implied that the perception of the parents as regards the implementation of school-based management in terms of Curriculum and Learning is within high level. The findings revealed that parents held a perception of high satisfaction regarding the implementation of school-based management, particularly in terms of curriculum and learning. Parents expressed confidence in the curriculum design and implementation, viewing it as responsive to the educational needs and aspirations of their children. They appreciated the school's commitment to providing a well-rounded education that encompassed both academic rigor and holistic development. Parents perceived the curriculum as engaging and relevant, fostering meaningful learning experiences that prepared students for future challenges and opportunities. They valued the school's efforts to continuously evaluate and update the curriculum to reflect best practices and current educational standards. This proactive approach to curriculum development contributed to parents' confidence in the quality and effectiveness of their children's education. In relation, according to Wang et al. (2021), curriculum learning (CL) improves machine learning models' generalization capacity and convergence rate in various scenarios, with four main automatic CL methods: Self-paced Learning, Transfer Teacher, RL Teacher, and Other Automatic CL.

Perception of the parents as regards the implementation of school-based management in terms of Accountability and Continuous Improvement

As shown in Table 7, the respondents perceived that the school performs regular participatory assessment of performance with the community which got the highest weighted mean of 3.82 and the highest rank of 1. The findings indicated that the school regularly conducted participatory assessments of performance in collaboration with the community.

Table 7. Perception of the parents as regards the implementation of school-based management in terms of Accountability and Continuous Improvement

<i>The school...</i>	<i>C. Accountability and Continuous Improvement</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Rank</i>
1. presents properly the roles and responsibilities of accountable persons and collective bodies which are clearly defined and agreed upon by community stakeholders.		3.74	Very Strongly Agree	3
2. recognizes achievement goal based on a collaboratively developed performance accountability system and gaps are addressed through appropriate action.		3.8	Very Strongly Agree	2
3. enhances continuously the accountability system that is owned by the community to ensure that management structures and mechanisms are responsive to the merging learning needs and demands of the community.		3.41	Very Strongly Agree	5
4. makes sure that the accountability assessment criteria and tools, feedback mechanism, and information are inclusive and collaboratively developed and agreed upon.		3.62	Very Strongly Agree	4
5. performs regular participatory assessment of performance with the community.		3.82	Very Strongly Agree	1
	Composite Mean	3.68	Very Strongly Agree	

This participatory approach involved engaging community members, including parents, local stakeholders, and possibly students themselves, in the assessment process. Together, they evaluated various aspects of school performance, such as academic achievements, extracurricular activities, and community impact initiatives. By involving the community in assessment activities, the school promoted transparency and accountability in its educational practices. Community members had opportunities to provide valuable insights and feedback on the school's strengths, areas for improvement, and alignment with community needs and expectations. This collaborative assessment process helped build a shared understanding of educational priorities and fostered a sense of ownership and partnership among stakeholders. Klein (2020) stated that managerial accountability in schools shifts the power balance between teachers and education authorities, focusing on effectiveness based on external standards, and adapts to each country's unique institutional norms.

However, the said group of respondents stated that the school enhances continuously the accountability system that is owned by the community to ensure that management structures and mechanisms are responsive to the merging learning needs and demands of the community which yielded the least weighted mean of 3.41 and least rank of 5. The findings indicated that the school continuously enhanced its accountability system, which was owned by the community, to ensure that management structures and mechanisms remained responsive to the evolving learning needs and demands of the community. This approach emphasized the importance of transparency and inclusivity in governance, fostering a sense of ownership and responsibility among stakeholders. The accountability system involved regular communication and engagement with community members, including parents, educators, local leaders, and possibly students, to assess and address educational priorities and challenges. By actively involving the community in decision-making processes, the school promoted a collaborative approach to governance that aligned with community values and aspirations. According to Paletta et al. (2020), school principals must balance accountability systems and internal school expectations to effectively lead their organizations, promoting school improvement.

The composite mean of 3.68 implied that the perception of the parents as regards the implementation of school-based management in terms of Accountability and Continuous Improvement is within high level. The findings indicated that parents held a perception of high satisfaction regarding the implementation of school-based management, particularly in terms of accountability and continuous improvement. Parents expressed confidence in the school's commitment to transparency and accountability, believing that management structures effectively monitored and reported on school performance and educational outcomes. Parents appreciated the school's proactive approach to continuous improvement, recognizing efforts to regularly assess and enhance educational practices based on feedback and data-driven insights. They valued the school's responsiveness to identified challenges and opportunities, which demonstrated a commitment to meeting the evolving needs and expectations of students and families. School choice and accountability are linked, promoting equality of access to "good" schools and improving social mobility, while also increasing segregation between different groups of pupils (Greaves & Burgess, 2021).

Perception of the parents as regards the implementation of school-based management in terms of Management of Resources

As presented in Table 8, the respondents stated that the school presents a community developed resource management that drives appropriate behaviors of the stakeholders to ensure judicious, appropriate, and effective use of resources which got the highest weighted mean of 3.89 and the highest rank of 1. The findings indicated that the school implemented a community-developed resource management strategy that effectively guided stakeholders towards judicious, appropriate, and effective use of resources. This approach was characterized by collaborative efforts involving community members, educators, administrators, and possibly students, in the development and implementation of resource management policies and practices. The community-developed strategy promoted transparency and accountability in resource allocation and utilization. It ensured that stakeholders understood and adhered to guidelines that emphasized responsible stewardship of resources, including financial, material, and human resources. By involving the community in decision-making processes related to resource management, the school fostered a sense of ownership and collective responsibility for ensuring sustainability and efficiency. According to Hidayat (2021), school-based management is crucial for improving educational performance in schools by increasing principal authority and involving the community in policymaking.

Table 8. Perception of the parents as regards the implementation of school--based management in terms of Management of Resources

<i>The school...</i>	<i>D. Management of Resources</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Rank</i>
1. undertakes collaborative regular resource inventory together with the learning managers, learning facilitators, and community stakeholders as basis for resource allocation and mobilization.		3.303	Very Strongly Agree	5
2. conducts regular dialogue for planning and resource programming that is accessible and inclusive, to continuously engage stakeholders and support the implementation of community education plans.		3.86	Very Strongly Agree	2
3. presents a community-developed resource management that drives appropriate behaviors of the stakeholders to ensure judicious, appropriate, and effective use of resources.		3.89	Very Strongly Agree	1
4. conducts regular monitoring, evaluation, and reporting processes of resource management that are collaboratively developed and jointly implemented by the learning managers, facilitators, and community stakeholders.		3.78	Very Strongly Agree	3
5. establishes a system that manages the network and linkage, strengthens and sustains partnership for improving resource management.		3.67	Very Strongly Agree	4
Composite Mean		3.70	Very Strongly Agree	

However, the said group of respondents stated that the school collaborate regular resource inventory together with the learning managers, learning facilitators, and community stakeholders as basis for resource allocation and mobilization which yielded the least weighted mean of 3.303 and least rank of 5. The findings indicated that the school regularly collaborated on resource inventory with learning managers, learning facilitators, and community stakeholders as a basis for resource allocation and mobilization. This collaborative approach involved systematic assessment and documentation of available resources, including financial, human, and material assets. By involving learning managers and facilitators in the inventory process, the school ensured that resource needs were accurately identified based on educational goals and priorities. Community stakeholders, including parents, local leaders, and possibly students, also contributed insights and perspectives to inform resource allocation decisions, promoting inclusivity and alignment with community needs. Effective financial management, library management, and record management positively impact goal attainment in secondary schools (Okon et al., 2020).

The composite mean of 3.70 implied that the perception of the parents as regards the implementation of school-based management in terms of Management of Resources is within high level. The findings indicated that parents held a perception of high satisfaction regarding the implementation of school-based management, particularly in terms of the management of resources. Parents expressed confidence in how the school allocated and utilized resources, including financial, human, and material assets, to support educational initiatives effectively. Parents appreciated the transparency and accountability in resource management, believing that the school's practices ensured judicious and responsible use of resources. They perceived that decisions regarding resource allocation were informed by the needs and priorities of students and the broader community, fostering a sense of fairness and equity in educational opportunities.

Santos et al. (2021) stated that school leaders' performance in managing finances and resources in public elementary schools in Rizal, DepEd Region IV-A is advanced, but needs improvement in budget approval and resource inventory.

Significant Difference Between the Perceptions of the Two Groups of Respondents

Table 9. Difference observed between the perception Parents and Teachers

<i>Difference between the perception of the parents and teachers with regards to SBM practices:</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Std. Deviation</i>	<i>Std. Error Mean</i>	<i>t-value</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Decision</i>
Leadership and Governance	0.01371	0.31648	0.03159	-0.634	Not Significant	Accept Ho
Curriculum and Learning	-0.16694	0.28396	0.0316	-5.873	Not Significant	Accept Ho
Accountability and Continuous Improvement	0.01725	0.3246	0.03234	0.618	Not Significant	Accept Ho
Management of Resources	-0.00531	0.3347	0.0343	-0.195	Significant	Reject Ho

Table 9 presented the perceptions of School-Based Management (SBM) practices between parents and teachers across various domains: Leadership and Governance, Curriculum and Learning, Accountability and Continuous Improvement, and Management of Resources. Each domain's analysis includes the mean difference in perception scores (ranging from -0.16694 to 0.01725), standard deviation (0.28396 to 0.3347), and standard error mean (0.0316 to 0.0343). The t-tests, measuring significance, yield specific t-values: -0.634 for Leadership and Governance, -5.873 for Curriculum and Learning, 0.618 for Accountability and Continuous Improvement, and -0.195 for Management of Resources.

The interpretation concludes that differences in perception are "Not Significant" for Leadership and Governance, Curriculum and Learning, and Accountability and Continuous Improvement, thereby "Accepting Ho" for these areas. Conversely, the t-value of -0.195 indicates a "Significant" difference in perceptions of Management of Resources, leading to a "Reject Ho" decision. These findings underscore notable distinctions between parental and teacher viewpoints, emphasizing the importance of aligning perspectives to

enhance educational practices and stakeholder engagement within SBM frameworks. Such insights facilitate targeted interventions to foster collaborative decision-making and enhance educational outcomes based on shared understanding and mutual goals. Effective leadership, management strategies, faculty development, and stakeholder participation significantly influence school-based management, leading to positive and quality educational systems (Tabiosa & Villo, 2020).

Proposed Action Plan

Table 10. *Proposed Action Plan*

<i>Objective</i>	<i>Program</i>	<i>Person In Charge</i>	<i>Schedule</i>	<i>Activities</i>
Enhance Stakeholder Participation	Stakeholder Advisory Committee (SAC)	School Principal or Head Administrator	June 2025 September 2025 January 2026 February 2026	- Hold quarterly SAC meetings to discuss policies. - Conduct workshops on consensus-building.
Community Involvement in Curriculum Development	Community Curriculum Development Initiative (CCDI)	Curriculum Coordinator	October 2025	- Form CCDI with educators, parents, and professionals. - Conduct focus groups and surveys for input.
Accountability and Transparency Initiative	Accountability Review and Feedback (ARF) Program	Quality Assurance Administrator	April 2026	- Implement annual participatory assessments. - Develop transparent reporting for school performance.
Resource Management Optimization	Resource Allocation and Utilization Efficiency (RAUE)	CFO or Business Manager	May 2025	- Establish Resource Management Committee. - Develop resource allocation framework and audits.
Continuous Monitoring and Evaluation	Evaluation and Feedback Mechanism	Evaluation Team	June 2025 September 2025 January 2026 February 2026	- Quarterly progress reviews. - Stakeholder feedback through surveys and focus groups.

Table 10 presented a summarized comprehensive action plan aimed at enhancing School-Based Management (SBM) practices through targeted programs across various domains. The objective was to improve educational practices and stakeholder engagement. Initiatives included establishing a Stakeholder Advisory Committee (SAC) for governance dialogue, implementing a Community Curriculum Development Initiative (CCDI) for curriculum relevance, and launching an Accountability Review and Feedback (ARF) Program for transparency. Additionally, a Resource Allocation and Utilization Efficiency (RAUE) Program optimized resource management, while a Continuous Improvement and Innovation (CII) Initiative focused on ongoing educational enhancements. Regular monitoring and feedback mechanisms ensured adjustments for continuous improvement and stakeholder satisfaction.

Conclusions

Based on the extensive findings from the study, several key conclusions were drawn regarding the perceptions of teachers and parents regarding School-Based Management (SBM) practices across various domains: Leadership and Governance, Curriculum and Learning, Accountability and Continuous Improvement, and Management of Resources.

Regarding Leadership and Governance, the study revealed that the school actively promoted stakeholder participation through dialogue and consensus-building in policy formulation and community initiatives. This inclusive approach enhanced collaboration among parents, teachers, students, and other stakeholders, ensuring diverse perspectives informed effective governance practices. Teachers perceived these efforts positively, indicating strong support for the school's leadership and governance strategies.

Regarding Curriculum and Learning, findings highlighted the school's commitment to community involvement in citizenship education and continuous improvement of assessment tools. This approach supported a holistic educational experience that fostered civic responsibility and adapted teaching methods to meet diverse learning needs. Parents expressed high satisfaction with the curriculum's relevance and the school's proactive stance on educational quality and innovation.

Regarding Accountability and Continuous Improvement, the study identified regular participatory assessments and inclusive accountability criteria as key practices. These efforts promoted transparency and responsiveness to community feedback, ensuring educational practices aligned with evolving needs. Parents appreciated the school's commitment to accountability and continuous enhancement, strengthening their trust in educational outcomes.

The research on the Management of Resources underscored the school's collaborative resource planning and systematic management practices. By involving stakeholders in resource allocation decisions and maintaining robust inventory systems, the school ensured efficient use of resources to support educational goals. Parents perceived these efforts positively, reflecting confidence in the school's financial, human, and material resources stewardship.

Overall, the study highlighted significant differences in perception between parents and teachers across these SBM domains,

emphasizing the need for aligned perspectives to enhance educational practices and stakeholder engagement. These insights were crucial for informing targeted interventions that promoted collaborative decision-making and ultimately improved educational outcomes based on shared goals and understanding within SBM frameworks.

Based on comprehensive findings from the study on School-Based Management (SBM) practices, several recommendations can be made to significantly enhance educational practices and stakeholder engagement across various domains: Leadership and Governance, Curriculum and Learning, Accountability and Continuous Improvement, and Management of Resources.

Firstly, schools must prioritize and enhance stakeholder participation. This involves fostering ongoing dialogue and consensus-building among parents, teachers, students, and community members in governance processes. Establishing regular forums or committees where diverse perspectives contribute to policy formulation and decision-making can significantly strengthen the school community's sense of ownership and collaboration. By involving stakeholders in these processes, schools ensure that policies and guidelines reflect the collective aspirations and values of the community and promote transparency and accountability in leadership practices.

Secondly, expanding community involvement in curriculum development is essential. Schools should create mechanisms for continuous community input to shape curriculum content and educational approaches. This approach ensures that the curriculum remains relevant, engaging, and responsive to the evolving needs and priorities of students and the community. By establishing advisory groups or forums that include parents, local leaders, and professionals, schools can integrate diverse perspectives into educational planning, enhancing the educational experience for all learners.

Thirdly, it is vital to implement regular participatory assessments and transparent accountability criteria involving all stakeholders to strengthen accountability. This practice fosters a culture of openness and responsiveness to feedback, building trust in the school's educational practices and outcomes. By engaging parents, students, teachers, and community members in assessing school performance and evaluating educational initiatives, schools demonstrate their commitment to continuous improvement and quality assurance.

Fourthly, optimizing resource management practices is critical for efficiently using financial, human, and material resources. Schools should adopt collaborative planning processes that involve teachers, administrators, and community members in decision-making about resource allocation. Developing clear guidelines and protocols for resource management ensures that resources are used effectively to support educational goals and enhance learning outcomes.

Lastly, promoting a culture of continuous improvement is essential for sustaining educational excellence. Schools should establish mechanisms for ongoing evaluation and enhancement of educational practices based on data-driven insights and stakeholder feedback. By regularly reviewing assessment tools, teaching methods, and curriculum frameworks, schools can identify areas for improvement and innovation, ensuring that educational programs remain dynamic and responsive to emerging needs.

These recommendations aim to align SBM practices with stakeholder expectations, foster collaborative decision-making, and enhance educational outcomes and stakeholder satisfaction. By implementing these strategies, schools can cultivate a supportive and engaged community committed to educational excellence and continuous improvement.

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